

Chemical speciation studies on the complexation of ditopic ligands : Interaction of malonic acid dihydrazide with some divalent transition metal ions in aqueous medium

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Abstract : Speciation study on the interaction of malonic acid dihydrazide with Mn^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} was carried out in aqueous medium at 303 K and 0.1 mol dm⁻³ ionic strength. The ditopic ligand possesses a number of potential donor atoms and is able to form both mono-nuclear and binuclear species in protonated, unprotonated and deprotonated forms. Best-fit chemical models representing the systems of different compositions were obtained using Miniquad-75 computer program. The species distribution diagrams were generated using HYSS program.

Keywords : Speciation, formation constant, malonic acid dihydrazide, metal complex.

Introduction

Chemists have long been interested¹ in bimetallic complexes that contain two or more different metal centers since they outperform²⁻⁴ the mono-nuclear catalysts. Dihydrazides and their derivatives are found to act as ditopic ligands which can accommodate two metal ions in different coordination pockets leading to the formation of bimetallic complexes. The presence of two coordinating sites separated by a flexible bridging part of the ligand may lead to supramolecular structure such as double helices. The selectivity and specificity achieved by nature in biological systems is certainly due to the formation of such complexes. Metal complexes of dihydrazides of malonic acid and its derivatives were found to show good biological activity⁵⁻⁹. Metal complexes of diacetyl salicylaldehyde and diacetyl benzaldehyde hydrazones of succinic, oxalic and malonic acid dihydrazides were found to have antifungal and antibacterial activity^{10,11}. Zn^{II} and Fe^{III} complexes of hydrazone derived from 2-acetylpyridine and oxalic or malonic acid dihydrazide exhibited high cytotoxic activity on HeLa and B16 cell cultures *in vitro*¹². This activity was assumed to be due to the strong bonding of the binuclear complex to DNA¹³. Dihydrazide contains two hydrazide groups and each hydrazide group

is known to exist either in ketonic [$NH_2.NH.C(=O).R.C(=O).NH.NH_2$] or enolic [$NH_2.N=C(OH).R.C(OH)=N.NH_2$] form. Depending on the pH the terminal amino groups of the neutral ligand may be protonated. These ligands may also lose protons from enolic form either at higher pH or on interaction with metal ions. Hence there is a chance of formation of a variety of coexisting mono-nuclear and binuclear species in protonated, unprotonated and deprotonated forms. The formation of binuclear species has special significance. The presence of two metal ions in the same species separated by some distance not too far, leads to several interesting and important applications¹ including unusual magnetic properties¹⁴. They can be used to mimic metalloproteins and to study structure-reactivity relationships¹. The metal centers are found to act synergistically in catalyzing reactions^{2,3}.

Most of the studies reported in the literature on metal complexes of dihydrazides were aimed at the synthesis and elucidation of structures by physicochemical methods¹⁵⁻²⁰. Relatively a few reports were found in literature on the solution equilibria of the metal complexes of dihydrazides^{21,22}. Chemical modeling study in which the nature and extent of formation of all the species can be

determined when a ligand interacts with metal ions in solution is an essential pre-requisite to understand their behavior in biological and other systems. Therefore, in this paper we report the results of a speciation study on the interaction of malonic acid dihydrazide (MADH) with Mn^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} in aqueous medium.

Experimental

Reagents and equipment :

Malonic acid dihydrazide (MADH) (Fluka) was recrystallized twice from water, dried at 100 °C and a $\sim 0.05 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ solution was prepared freshly in 0.1 mol dm^{-3} HCl just before the titrations. All the metal ion solutions (Mn^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Cu^{2+} and Zn^{2+}) were prepared from the corresponding chlorides (B.D.H., AnalaR) and were standardized by conventional complexometric titrations²³. An overall 0.01 mol dm^{-3} HCl was maintained in all the metal ion solutions to repress the hydrolysis²⁴. The acid contents of the metal solutions were determined by titration with 0.1 mol dm^{-3} NaOH solutions after liberation of the H^+ ions by cation exchange²⁵. A $\sim 0.2 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ solution of sodium hydroxide (E. Merck proanalysis) was prepared in double distilled water and was standardized against potassium hydrogen phthalate (Merck). It was then preserved under nitrogen atmosphere and regularly Gran-titrated to check the absence of carbonates^{26,27}. Solution of $\sim 0.2 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ hydrochloric acid (E. Merck proanalysis), prepared by successive dilutions was standardized against sodium hydroxide solution. All potentiometric titrations were carried out in aqueous medium at an ionic strength of 0.1 mol dm^{-3} using NaCl (B.D.H., AnalaR) as the background electrolyte.

A Control Dynamics pH meter model APX 175 E/C in conjunction with a combination electrode (0–14 pH range) was used for pH measurements. The electrode system was standardized in terms of hydrogen ion concentration in aqueous solution. The correction factor to convert the pH meter dial reading into logarithm of reciprocal of hydrogen ion concentration was calculated before each set of experimental titrations by performing an acid base titration at the chosen ionic strength and analyzing the data by Gran method and ACBA²⁸ computer program.

A tip-less double walled Pyrex glass vessel of 100 ml

capacity fitted with a perspex lid, through which the combined glass electrode, gas inlet and outlet tubes and burette tip were admitted, was used for carrying out the potentiometric titrations. The temperature of the solution was maintained by passing thermostatted water through the annular space between the walls of the titration cell. The experimental solution was earthed by means of a platinum wire sealed in a glass tube. In order to prevent the introduction of an earth loop, the pH meter, thermostat and magnetic stirrer were earthed to the same terminal. Purified nitrogen gas was passed through the experimental solution both before and during titration to expel carbon dioxide.

Data acquisition and analysis :

Calvin-Wilson titration technique as modified by Irving and Rossotti^{29,30} was used for the study of protonation and complex equilibria of the ligand (MADH). Requisite volumes of hydrochloric acid (to give an overall concentration of $2.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$), sodium chloride (to maintain ionic strength at 0.1 mol dm^{-3}) and ligand solution in a total volume of 50.0 cm^3 was titrated with $\sim 0.2 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ sodium hydroxide at $30 \pm 1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The concentration of the ligand was 0.004 to $0.015 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ in different experiments. The same titrations were repeated in the presence of metal ion at 1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 2 : 1 ratios of initial concentrations of metal to ligand. After addition of each aliquot (0.1 ml) of sodium hydroxide, the pH-meter dial reading was recorded at regular intervals of time until two successive readings do not differ in more than 0.01 pH units. The titrations were performed up to a pH of ~ 12.0 . In some of the titrations, the upper pH limit for rejecting data was determined by the appearance of opalescence leading to precipitation.

For a system containing a metal ion and a ligand forming N complexes, the formation of a complex can be represented as,

and the overall formation constant is given by,

$$\beta_{mlh} = [M_m L_l H_h]_i / [M]_i^m \cdot [L]_i^l \cdot [H]_i^h$$

where $[M]_i$, $[L]_i$ and $[H]_i$ are the free concentrations of metal, ligand and hydrogen ion respectively at i -th experimental point. Different species in solution possess

different values of stoichiometric coefficients m , l and h . Positive value of h indicates protonated species and negative value indicates either deprotonated or hydroxylated species. Several computer programs have been proposed for the evaluation of both stoichiometric coefficients and formation constants for all the species present in solution. Most of these algorithms are based on the minimization of error square sum (U) between the experimentally determined quantities and the corresponding calculated ones using the estimated values of the formation constants. The values of the formation constants obtained by graphical procedures are taken as initial estimates. The computer based algorithms generate a vector of shifts to the formation constants and free concentrations. The modified constants after applying the shifts are then used as the initial estimates for the next cycle. If the chosen model is a true representation of the system and the initial estimates of formation constants are not far from the true values, the iteration will converge in a finite number of cycles. The procedure is repeated for different chemical models and the best-fit model is selected basing on the statistical parameters. The potentiometric titration data obtained in the present investigation was subjected to analysis by Miniquad-75 program³¹. This program is robust and uses both constrained least-squares and Marquardt methods to achieve convergence even in extreme cases of non-convergence. Species distribution diagrams for all the systems under study were generated using HYSS³² program. The data from different experiments with different metal to ligand ratios were refined separately using Miniquad-75 program to yield species relevant to that particular composition. This way of refinement has been found to be better³³ compared to analysing the combined data from all the titrations at a time since the main part of the error in the stability constants derives from the variability from one titration to another. Therefore, the authors processed the data from different compositions separately using Miniquad-75 program. The best-fit models were selected on the basis of U (sum of the squares of residuals in mass balance equations), standard deviations in formation constants and other statistics like χ^2 test which tests the distribution of errors against a normal one.

Results and discussion

Proton-ligand equilibria of malonic acid dihydrazide :

The protonation and deprotonation equilibria of MADH are shown in Fig. 1. The best-fit model obtained using Miniquad-75 program (Table 1) contained three stability constants β_{011} , β_{012} and β_{01-1} corresponding to the formation of LH_2 , LH and LH_{-1} .

Below pH ~ 2.0 MADH (L) mostly exists in diprotonated form LH_2^{2+} and with rise in pH undergoes successive deprotonation to form the mono-protonated (LH^+) and neutral species (L). β_{011} and β_{012} are the formation constants (Fig. 1) of mono and diprotonated forms of MADH respectively, the protonation being at the terminal nitrogen atoms of the two hydrazide groups. The species distribution diagram of MADH (Fig. 2) indicates that the species LH^+ exists in solution up to a pH of ~ 6.0 with a maximum of 81.3% at pH 2.7 and the entire ligand is in neutral form (L) between ~ 6.0 and ~ 9.0 pH.

In the basic medium hydrazides are prone to lose a proton³⁴ from the enolic form. As MADH contains two hydrazide groups, there is a chance of losing two enolic protons at higher pH. The formation constant, β_{01-1} in the best-fit model corresponds to the deprotonation of one of the enolic protons leading to the formation of LH_{-1} species. This species appears in solution only above a pH of ~ 9.0 . The formation constant, β_{01-2} which corresponds to the deprotonation of the second enolic group leading to the formation of LH_{-2} , is not converged. This is because its equilibrium may lie well above the pH range of the study. However, in the presence of a metal ion the ligand may also lose the second enolic proton forming both deprotonated $M_mL_lH_{-1}$ and $M_mL_lH_{-2}$ type of species.

Metal-ligand equilibria :

The potentiometric titration data for 1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 2 : 1 metal to ligand concentration ratios for different metal ions was used to calculate the formation constants of both mono-nuclear and binuclear complexes. The acquired data was first subjected to analysis by classical procedures²⁹ to get the formation constants of simple mono-nuclear complexes like ML , ML_2 etc. Simulated titration curves were then generated using a computer program SOPHD³⁵ developed in our laboratory to see

Fig. 1. Protonation and deprotonation equilibria of MADH.

Table 1. Protonation constants of MADH in aqueous medium				
Temp. = 30 ± 1 °C and ionic strength, $I = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (NaCl)				
Species	$\log \beta_{0th}$ (SD)	Number of experimental points analysed	Sum of the squares of residuals, U	χ^2
011	03.47 (0.03)	89	3.99×10^{-7}	21.28
012	05.94 (0.07)			
01-1	-10.80 (0.05)			

SD = Standard deviation.

whether these species satisfy the experimental data. The simulated titration curves thus obtained were plotted along with the experimental ones to identify the regions of pH where they differ. Titration curves for some representa-

tive systems for all the compositions are shown in Fig. 3. The wide difference between the simulated and experimental curves reveals the presence of other major species in addition to simple mono-nuclear complexes. Different chemical models containing chemically plausible species depending on the nature of the ligand, metal and the pH region of difference in the curves were tested using the Miniquad-75 program. The required initial estimates of the formation constants were calculated basing on the formation constants of simple complexes and protonation/deprotonation constants of the ligand.

The results of the analysis i.e. the stoichiometry and the overall formation constants of various species giving the best fit to the experimental data for all the systems are

Fig. 2. Species distribution diagram for proton-ligand equilibria of MADH (L).

given in Table 2. The best-fit models contain protonated, unprotonated and deprotonated mono-nuclear and binuclear species. The formation constants are in good agreement with Irving-Williams order^{36,37} i.e. $Mn^{II} < Co^{II} < Ni^{II} < Cu^{II} > Zn^{II}$.

The species distribution diagrams for metal-ligand systems (Fig. 4) give the percentage of formation of various species as a function of pH. For 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 compositions at pH below ~4.0, the protonated species MLH, ML₂H and ML₂H₂ are prevalent for all the metal ions under study. In the case of protonated species MLH and ML₂H₂ probably only one of the hydrazide groups of the MADH (L) is involved in bonding as a bidentate^{38,39} bonding through carbonyl oxygen and terminal nitrogen. The other hydrazide group is protonated at the terminal nitrogen. The species ML₂H₂ with increase in pH loses a proton on non-bonding side and forms ML₂H. Beyond pH 4.0 simple complexes like ML and ML₂ appear in

Fig. 3. Simulated and experimental titration curves for (a) cobalt(II)-MADH and (b) nickel(II)-MADH systems for 1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 2 : 1 compositions : (1) Simulated titration curve, (2) Experimental titration curve.

Table 2. Best-fit models for MADH-metal ion systems

Temp. = 30 ± 1 °C and ionic strength, $I = 0.1$ mol dm⁻³

Concentration ratio M : L	Species <i>mlh</i>	log β_{mlh} (SD) ^a				
		Mn ^{II}	Co ^{II}	Ni ^{II}	Cu ^{II}	Zn ^{II}
1 : 1	111	6.79 (2)	7.14 (2)	7.83 (6)	8.28 (2)	7.29 (3)
	110	3.33 (2)	3.71 (1)	4.79 (4)	6.44 (10)	3.84 (2)
	11-1	-4.64 (2)	-4.60 (8)	-2.04 (5)	2.36 (11)	-
	11-2	-	-11.94 (9)	-9.71 (4)	-4.92 (11)	-9.99 (2)
1 : 2	122	13.75 (6)	13.76 (3)	14.94 (5)	15.66 (11)	14.23 (5)
	121	-	-	11.61 (11)	13.54 (9)	-
	120	6.60 (12)	7.10 (6)	9.17 (10)	10.35 (13)	7.34 (7)
	12-1	-1.40 (13)	-0.031 (6)	2.51 (10)	4.60 (13)	-0.11 (9)
	12-2	-9.44 (11)	-8.05 (5)	-4.85 (10)	-2.68 (13)	-6.76 (7)
2 : 1	111	-	7.14	7.83	8.28	-
	210	5.85 (7)	5.98 (7)	7.01 (2)	9.47 (6)	5.56 (8)
	21-1	-2.17 (10)	-1.43 (9)	-0.33 (5)	6.27 (6)	-
	21-2	-10.60 (8)	-9.08 (7)	-6.74 (2)	2.27 (6)	-7.80 (7)

^aSD = Standard deviation in the least significant digit.

Fig. 4. Species distribution diagrams of M^{II}-MADH systems for 1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 2 : 1 (M : L) concentration ratios : (a) Mn^{II}-MADH, (b) Co^{II}-MADH, (c) Ni^{II}-MADH, (d) Cu^{II}-MADH, (e) Zn^{II}-MADH.

solutions of compositions 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 (M : L), in which neutral form of MADH participates in complexation as a bidentate bonding through carbonyl oxygen and terminal nitrogen atom. The percentage of formation of these species reaches 80–97% for different metal ions. With increase in pH these species also lose protons and form deprotonated species like MLH_{-1} , MLH_{-2} , ML_2H_{-1} , ML_2H_{-2} etc. The formation of these species may be due to the participation of deprotonated enolic form (Fig. 1) of the ligand in bonding.

In the case of 2 : 1 metal to ligand concentration ratio, all the metal-MADH systems exhibit the formation of homo binuclear complexes, where MADH acts as a ditopic ligand and is attached to two metal ions either in neutral or deprotonated enolic form. Although solution phase studies of speciation can not give the exact structure of a complex, a probable general structure of binuclear complex supported by solid state studies⁴⁰ is shown in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5. Bimetallic complexes of malonic acid dihydrazide.

The coordination of a metal ion by one unit of the ligand may affect the coordination at the other unit. This leads to the formation of unsymmetrical complexes where the mode of coordination is different at the two structurally identical units of the same ligand. This was observed in the case of M_2LH_{-1} type of species where the two hydrazide groups of the ligand are involved in bonding differently one in neutral form and the other in deprotonated enolic form.

The extent of formation of symmetric M_2L type of species ranges from 75–92% of total metal for different metal ions in the pH range of study. The ligand acts as bis bidentate coordinating through carbonyl oxygen and $-NH_2$ groups forming five membered rings on both sides^{5,38}. In the case of copper(II), the species Cu_2L already formed to about ~60% at the starting experimental pH reaches to a maximum of 75% at 2.2 pH. Beyond this range deprotonation of M_2L takes place for all the metal ions leading to the formation of M_2LH_{-1} and M_2LH_{-2} type of species.

Conclusion

The results obtained clearly indicate that malonic acid dihydrazide (L) possesses a number of potential donor atoms and also acts as a ditopic ligand. Depending on the pH the ligand exists in various protonated and deprotonated forms, LH_2^{2+} , LH^+ , L, LH_{-1}^- and LH_{-2}^{2-} . The protonation is at the terminal nitrogen atoms of the hydrazide groups and deprotonation is from the enolic forms at higher pH. On interaction with metal ions in solution, a series of mononuclear $[M(LH_h)]$ ($h = 1, 0, -1, -2$), bis-mononuclear $[M(L_2H_h)]$ ($h = 2, 1, 0, -1, -2$) and homo-binuclear $[M_2(LH_h)]$ ($h = 0, -1, -2$) species were identified. The formation constants and species distribution indicate strong complexation in most of the cases.

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